

Immune Mediated Inflammatory Disease (IMID) Data Catalyst Workshop report – January 2024

Foreword

Immune mediated inflammatory diseases (IMIDs) are common, chronic disabling disorders affecting more than 4.7 million people in the UK, they comprise a wide range of disorders including inflammatory skin diseases such as psoriasis, inflammatory joint diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis, and inflammatory bowel disease such as Crohn's disease. Current clinical and research approaches to IMIDs are characteristically siloed, focused on disease specific areas. This approach misses a key opportunity afforded by similar pathophysiological and therapeutic characteristics. IMIDs are a key area of rapid therapeutic innovation. This expanded repertoire of available and effective drugs brings both opportunities and challenges.

Addressing the need to move away from siloed care and research, we formed a collaborative group emerging from the pandemic Immune Mediated Inflammatory Disease Taskforce and devised a workshop in partnership with Health Data Research UK (HDR UK). The goals of the workshop were to bring together a wide community of stakeholders to identify what the key barriers and priorities were in terms of data access and linkages to enable transformative research which will ultimately lead to better patient outcomes.

Sinéad Langan, Cathie Sudlow, Iain McInnes, Rhos Walker

Introduction

The aim of the workshop was to bring together a wide range of stakeholders including patients, charities, researchers and clinicians with a special interest in immune mediated inflammatory diseases, health data experts and regulatory bodies to discuss the key ambitions and opportunities in health and care data to deliver benefits for patients with Immune Mediated Inflammatory Diseases (IMIDs).

The workshop was held at the Wellcome Trust on 22nd January 2024. Following short talks from a range of stakeholders, the majority of the meeting was focused on small group discussions with a view to addressing and agreeing our key objectives as outlined below.

Objectives:

1. Secure agreement and commitment from key stakeholders that the efficient use of health-related data represents a critical opportunity for the UK IMID health and research community.
2. Agree justification for a sustainable cross-IMID data collaboration, enabling programmes that can inform understanding of therapeutics, care pathways, and pharmacovigilance.
3. Determine the top data priorities for the IMID community that can benefit from investment in data science, and consider the functionality and connectivity needed to answer priority research questions.

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Background

The first component of the workshop was a series of short talks as summarised below.

- **Health Data Research UK**

- HDR UK's primary purpose is to accelerate the trustworthy use of health data for research. This is achieved through a range of initiatives, with a focus on facilitating data access, curation and linkage. An important aspect of HDR UK's work is to capitalise on existing data, by supporting research which understands, utilises and improves available data resources, avoiding unnecessary duplication of effort. Through strategic funding partnerships, HDR UK's BHF Data Science Centre has successfully established infrastructure-focused data science catalyst activities to further enable health data research in diabetes and stroke. HDR UK is now expanding this approach to other areas, including renal, respiratory and neurodegenerative diseases.
- There are common generic health data needs of each domain or disease specific community. For these we should be building on what exists, using and improving existing infrastructures and adding the specific assets of, requirements of and value from the IMID community.

Cathie Sudlow

- **Immune Mediated Inflammatory Diseases**

- IMIDs are interconnected through common and distinct public and private pathways and therapeutic strategies and understanding the disease (and drug) specific differences (benefit, risk, mechanisms) is important as are the commonalities. Over the last two decades, and particularly in the last five years, therapies for these diseases have undergone significant changes, leading to a substantial improvement in health outcomes for individuals living with these conditions. This transformation has been driven by the advent of new therapeutics, developed from a deeper understanding of disease pathogenesis gleaned from a range of data, including single-cell sequencing data from genetic through to metabolomics.
- It is our responsibility to use these therapies effectively, in a cost-efficient and safe manner. We have a tremendous opportunity with patient charities, clinicians, researchers and regulators all collaborating in this endeavour. The recent COVID-19 pandemic has further highlighted our ability to unite across disease and therapeutic areas. A key example of pioneering work integrating datasets from primary and secondary care, and crucially therapeutic data from the specialist prescribing records was achieved by the OpenSAFELY team.²
- Our goal with this data catalyst is to establish a sustainable, cross-disease collaboration for immune mediated inflammatory diseases, with a clear vision of creating an agile research network. This network will focus on improving patient outcomes, always keeping the patient at the forefront of all our efforts.

Sinéad Langan and Iain McInnes

- **Lessons from other Data Catalysts**

- The journey of data in healthcare is a long and intricate process, beginning with the first patient interaction. This journey encompasses numerous steps: the collection and recording of data, the critical process of data cleaning (curation), linking to other data sets, ethical and regulatory approvals for data access, data analysis, the generation of insights, and the production of published outputs that might lead to changes in healthcare practice or health policy.
- It is notable that the vast majority of time in this data journey, is clustered, early on, particularly at the stages of data creation, data cleaning, and data access. The challenges encountered in this process are not merely technical. There is a substantial human element involved—and forming trusted relationships can make formal partnerships and collaborations possible. Crucially, patients and members of the public must be involved at the heart of these partnerships, providing meaningful input throughout the process.
- Recognising and adhering to common data standards and processes can significantly streamline this journey. This aspect has been highlighted by the HDR UK pillars, which focus not only on building new data sets but on transforming our existing infrastructure and the accessibility of data, as well as leveraging external funding. This approach aims to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of data use in health and care research and practice.

Figure 1.

One of HDR UK’s areas of focus is research data, infrastructure and services to unite health data. This will build on the UK Health Data Research Alliance and deliver through four pillars: Technology Services Ecosystem, Trust and Transparency, Useable Data, Capacity Building.

Figure 2.

Accelerating the researcher journey towards trustworthy use of health data

Rhos Walker, Aziz Sheikh

- **Current Data Landscape**

- Immune mediated inflammatory diseases carry a high burden, not just due to the diseases themselves but also because of their associated co-morbidities, particularly impacting mental health. These diseases are associated with morbidity, early mortality and significantly impact on employment and work opportunities.
- It has been 25 years since the licensing of Infliximab, a milestone in this field. However, despite over two decades of research, our ability to predict outcomes for individual patients, including which drugs work for whom, remains limited. The Medical Research Council has invested substantial funds into the stratified medicines agenda, yet, progress has been somewhat hindered by the tendency to work within disease-specific silos.
- The BSR Biologic Register, established over 20 years ago, has been pivotal in studying the safety of biologics and delivering risk management information to regulators. It stands as a beacon in drug safety, having successfully collaborated with other European registries. However, maintaining disease registers requires considerable effort, including obtaining patient consent, the burden of data linkages and keeping up with renewal notices and contractual obligations with the NHS.
- An exemplar question has arisen in regards to JAK inhibitors, these drugs were first conceptualised in the 1990s and Tofacitinib was licensed for rheumatoid arthritis in the United States in 2012 with UK regulatory approval in 2017 ([6 January 2017 EMA/CHMP/32752/2017](#)). As it stands, there is an extensive list of JAK inhibitor drugs available in the UK for various autoimmune diseases. Concerns about potential side effects of this therapy class emerged in 2020, leading to blanket safety warnings across all disease indications. European societies for Crohn's and Colitis have raised concerns that this blanket approach fails to acknowledge varying risk-benefit ratios in different patient populations. This has underscored the urgent need for disease registries to examine these safety outcomes. However, in the UK, only a small number of patients started on JAK inhibitors are enrolled in registers.
- This situation presents challenges in finding data that allows us to examine drug response and safety, which are crucial for making personalised treatment decisions, especially when concerns about the risk-benefit ratio arise.

- Denmark serves as an exemplary model, where a data platform sharing clinical, genetic, and drug exposure data has been established, leading to significant advancements in predicting patient responses to treatments.
- Compared to other counterparts abroad, such as countries in Scandinavia, which have established comprehensive health data networks, the UK risks falling behind in our ability to study contemporary drug safety signals, such as the recent JAK inhibitor concerns. To maintain global leadership in this field and to provide the best outcomes for our patients, there is a clear opportunity for the UK to work together across the disease silos. This would enhance our understanding of how treatments affect different patient populations. Our patients not only support this academic venture, but also express surprise that such collaboration is not already standard practice.

Kimme Hyrich, Charlie Lees, Benjamin Ellis

Following the presentations, the substantive part of the workshop was focused on small group discussions followed by a wider conversation involving all stakeholders. These groups were facilitated by allocated rapporteurs and notetakers. Each group focused on the following three questions:

1. What are the priorities for a data catalyst for IMIDs?
2. What are the potential barriers and challenges in developing an IMID Data Catalyst?
3. What else should we be thinking about?

Following focus group discussions, all groups presented their key points to the plenary. Key topics that emerged from the session are outlined below from the perspective of different key stakeholder groups.

Stakeholder perspectives

RESEARCH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studying drug effectiveness and safety is rapidly evolving. • Registries are great for detailed disease phenotype but have limitations with respect to sample size and generalisability as they may only capture a potentially biased subset of patients starting new treatment. • Routinely collected data address the sample size issue but lack granularity on disease phenotypes and measures of disease severity. • Strategies such as trial emulation and in silico trials are evolving as mechanisms to address some of these challenges. • Need a life course approach to the question and ensure we have strategies relevant for different age groups. • Power of routinely collected data lies in the potential strength of linkage across broad NHS data repositories. Academic institutions' ownership of data or expertise in using a given data source can be seen as a competitive asset, which disincentives data sharing
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<p>CLINICAL IMPLEMENTATION</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to consider underrepresented populations, including rare IMIDs, conception and pregnancy, older patients, and children and young people and ensure analyses address culture/social diversity. • Outputs need to be timely rather than waiting more than a decade between licensing and emergence of signals. • Trials sometimes fail to address clinically relevant questions; for example, drugs are compared to placebo and populations are different. Head-to-head comparisons support clinical decisions, however these trials usually need to be larger and are commercially sensitive; need trials and real world data. • Real world data provides opportunities to address these knowledge gaps.
<p>REGULATORY</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data governance is crucial. • Secure data environments should be the norm for federated (i.e., using data from multiple sources) analyses. • Data environments need to be agile to address emergency safety signals. • Signal verification and subgroup analyses to identify populations at high risk. • Relationships with industry must be transparent. • Precedence exists for real world data influencing regulatory decisions. • Need to engage with regulators such as MHRA and NICE in the UK, EMA and FDA internationally.
<p>PATIENT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognise the importance of cross IMID collaboration. Commonalities and differences. • Treatment personalisation - Identifying when to step up and down. Consider safety of medicines by key characteristics. • Regularly revisit data curation assumptions • Barriers to data sharing must be overcome. • Needs to demonstrate direct benefit to clinical care e.g. during the pandemic knowing who should be shielding. If the data were joined up better this could have saved lives. • Concerns about industry incentives in collaborations - need to consider when and how. • Priority linkages- baby clinics, midwives, employment, pollution, economic data, asthma annual reviews.
<p>PATIENT CHARITY</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Charity funding is changing and legacy donors are reducing so resources are finite and precious in terms of funding. • Partnership across disease areas is an opportunity but not without challenges, and charities' foremost responsibility is to their

	<p>respective communities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong support that funding should be accompanied by requirements for data sharing and accessibility. • Recognise financial advantages of partnership with industry but need to ensure academic independence and integrity to ensure trustworthy outputs.
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Lessons learned and future intentions

The main learning from the workshop was that there was energy and enthusiasm in the room to support the concept of a Data Catalyst for IMIDs. Key points of consensus and detailed insights that emerged from the workshop are outlined below.

1. *We need to capitalise on the collaborations built during the pandemic*

During the pandemic, large informal groups of researchers worked together across disciplines and silos to deliver transformative research with benefits well beyond single disease areas or body systems, as exemplified by the IMID community. A key priority is that this momentum must be built on and expanded to ensure continued collaboration with ensuing benefits for patients and the public. We also need to respect the skills across diverse teams - not just of clinical/health researchers, but also software engineers, legal/ethical experts etc.

2. *We need to learn from existing data catalyst programmes*

A key principle is that a Data Catalyst for IMIDs should learn from and benefit from other Data Catalyst, Driver programmes and similar efforts to establish an accessible, enabling data infrastructure that can support multiple disease-areas, including ensuring that activity is not duplicated and redundant, maximising benefits from investments.

3. *We need to break down data silos within the NHS and across diseases*

We identified key silos and barriers that currently exist and began to outline how we could overcome those barriers. Key linkages and underserved populations and groups were identified in the workshop - these must be priority linkages as the Data Catalyst takes shape. This requires full stakeholder engagement and commitment, including engaging stakeholders that were not represented in the workshop for example, NHSE, Government and industry.

4. *We need to remain patient focused*

At the heart of this activity, engaging patients and the public is key to delivering an effective Data Catalyst capable of addressing questions that are relevant, in a trustworthy manner.

Why do we need to do this now?

1. New drugs
2. Expanded technical and data science capacity
3. Proof of concept established in the pandemic, but risk of slipping back to siloes
4. In response to patient and clinician expectations – in the era of precision medicine – being able to quantify risk and benefit

Concluding remarks

The IMID Data Catalyst workshop was a success, bringing together a wide range of stakeholders, and facilitating discussions to identify priorities, barriers and opportunities. We are grateful to all the stakeholders who contributed to this event.

In relation to workshop objectives, it is exciting to see that we have secured agreement and commitment from key stakeholders that efficient use of health-related data is a critical opportunity for the UK health and research community. The group agreed justification for a sustainable cross-IMID data collaboration, to enable programmes that can inform understanding of therapeutics, care pathways, trajectories and pharmacovigilance. We determined the top data priorities (see table of Stakeholder perspectives) for the IMID community, that can be furnished by investment in data science, and considered the functionality and connectivity needed to answer priority research questions.

The next steps will address how to work together to make this vision a reality. This workshop report serves as a consensus statement, on behalf of the community, to facilitate ongoing discussions with partners including HDR UK, UKRI - MRC, relevant medical research charities, regulators, and other funding organisations to support alignment with broader plans in IMID and health data research.

Key references

1. Gravallesse EM, McInnes. Advances abound in immune mediated inflammatory diseases. Seminars in Arthritis and Rheumatism.
2. MacKenna B, Kennedy NA, Mehrkar A, Rowan A, Galloway J, Matthewman J, Mansfield KE, Bechman K, Yates M, Brown J, Schultze A, Norton S, Walker AJ, Morton CE, Harrison D, Bhaskaran K, Rentsch CT, Williamson E, Croker R, Bacon S, Hickman G, Ward T, Davy S, Green A, Fisher L, Hulme W, Bates C, Curtis HJ, Tazare J, Eggo RM, Evans D, Inglesby P, Cockburn J, McDonald HI, Tomlinson LA, Mathur R, Wong AYS, Forbes H, Parry J, Hester F, Harper S, Douglas IJ, Smeeth L, Lees CW, Evans SJW, Goldacre B, Smith CH, Langan SM. Risk of severe COVID-19 outcomes associated with immune-mediated inflammatory diseases and immune-modifying therapies: a nationwide cohort study in the OpenSAFELY platform. *Lancet Rheumatol.* 2022;4(7):e490-e506.